

**DISTRIBUTION OF LAMBS FROM DIFFERENT MATING
OF KARAKUL SHEEP OF SUR COLOR, KARAKALPAK
TYPE INTO CLASSES**

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Abstract

This article presents the results of the experiment on the distribution of lambs obtained by homogeneous and heterogeneous mating of Karakul sheep of steel color.

Keywords: Sur, breed, type, heterogeneous, homogeneous, Karakul, elite, I-class, II-class

Introduction

The Karakul sheep breed is bred in more than 40 countries of the world, and among these countries, the Republic of South Afr Namibia, and Afghanistan are the countries with the highest level of Karakul breeding. The field of cattle breeding is also significantly developed in the Commonwealth of Nations. Especially in the countries of Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and Tajikistan, significant progress has been made as a result of the organizational, selection and scientific-research works on the development of this field. Among them, 5 highly productive factory types of Karakul sheep of different colors have been created in Turkmenistan, 3 in Tajikistan, and more than 15 in Kazakhstan. At the same time, Karakul sheep are bred in Russia, Ukraine and Moldavia, and they are characterized by specific productivity characteristics. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of scientists have conducted research on increasing the productivity of Karakul sheep and studying their biological characteristics. Among

them, D.M.Parmonova in her research emphasizes the difference in the quality characteristics of the offspring obtained from heterogeneous and homogeneous mating. According to the author, the amount of semicircle elite lambs was 22,8+5,0%, while the amount of class I lambs was 57,1+5,9%. These indicators prove to be much higher than heterogeneous pairing [1;].

Also, E.I.Refatova reports that Saribel factory-type lambs are superior in terms of flower type and class indicators compared to the local population, and it is necessary to use the features of stable reproduction in generations of silvery varieties [2;].

Today's demand is to increase the number of unique Karakul sheep species and improve their breeding grounds.

Therefore, one of the main tasks is to increase the number of Karakul sheep of the Karakalpak sur breed type, as well as to create a herd of highly productive specialized animals that will ensure the stable production of valuable and rare Karakul skins (Turganbaev.R). In this case, the skin class, which determines the quality of skins, is the main selection result [3;].

Research Address and Methods

The quality indicators of the lambs obtained from experimental sheep were evaluated on the basis of "Manual for conducting breeding work and evaluation (auditing) of lambs in Karakul breeding" (S. Yusupov et al., 2015) [4;]. Numerical data were processed based on the method of biometric processing according to the manual "Rukovodstvo biometryi dlya zootechnikov" (N.A. Ploxinsky (1969)) in the methods of variational statistics [5;].

Research Results

According to the results of our experimental work, the class of lambs obtained from the mating of Karakalpak Sur Karakul sheep with different color diversity is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

The distribution of Karakalpak sur lambs from different mating into classes
as a percentage

Types of mating	Number of animals	Elite	Class I	Class II	Invalid
		X±Sx			
ShGxPS	73	9,6±3,44	53,4±5,83	27,4±5,22	9,6±3,44
UGxPS	81	8,6±3,11	44,5±5,52	39,5±5,43	7,4±2,9
PSxPS	57	12,3±4,35	57,9±6,54	24,5±5,7	5,3±2,96
QSxPS	54	3,7±2,56	35,2±6,5	48,1±6,8	13,0±4,57

As can be seen from the data of Table 1, it is possible to observe the differences (in %) in the distribution of qoraqalpoq sur lambs in different mating classes. If the number of elite lambs in the generations obtained from the PSxPS mating was 12,3±4,35%, this indicator was 2,7% higher in the generations obtained from the ShGxPS mating compared to the homogenous mating of steelhead sheep, and 3,7% in the generations obtained from the UGxPS mating. It can be seen that QSxPS is 8,6% less than pairing

From the analysis of the table data, it can be said that the percentage of I-class lambs was 53,4±5,83%, and the percentage of unfit skins was 9,6±3,44% in the progeny obtained from the ShGxPS mating. This indicator, in our opinion, is due to the fact that in ShGxPS mating, the flowers of Sur Karakul are expressed, withdrawn, and the majority of worthless flowers are spread.

The proportion of unusable skins in offspring obtained from QSxPS mating was 13,0±4,57%. In addition, the distribution share of elite lambs was 3,7±2,56%. Such a result can be characterized by the fact that the lower part of the wool fiber is black or dark, gradually changing to reddish or brown color in black-colored black lambs. The percentage of elite + I class lambs with high-quality and high-

quality lambs in progeny obtained from heterogeneous and homogeneous matings is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The percentage of elite + I class lambs with high-quality and high-quality lambs in progenies obtained from heterogeneous and homogeneous matings, in %.

The percentage of lambs of elite + I class in offsprings obtained from PSxPS mating was confirmed to be 70,2%, which is higher than lambs obtained from ShGxPS, UGxPS and QSxPS matings. This indicator was 63,0%, 53,1% and 38,9%, respectively.

Summary

Based on the results of the research, it can be concluded that the number of elite lambs in the generations obtained from the PSxPS mating was $12,3 \pm 4,35\%$, this indicator was 2,7% in the generations obtained from the ShGxPS mating compared to the homogenous mating of the steel brown sheep, and in the

generations obtained from the UGxPS mating and it can be seen that it is 3,7% less than QSxPS pairing by 8,6%. Based on the results of the research, it is Possible to use the "homogeneous" method in breeding Karakalpak Sur sheep and to increase the share of elite + I class lambs to 65-70%

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